

Non-terpenoidal constituents of *Azadirachta indica* root bark[†]

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Abstract : A new steroid named as margocidin (1) has been isolated from the neutral fraction of the methylene chloride extract of neem roots along with the known 3 β -hydroxy stigmast-5-en-7-one (2) and ferula aldehyde (3) hitherto unreported from any of the various parts of neem tree. The structures of these compounds have been determined through chemical and spectroscopic methods. The fatty acid components of petrol soluble fraction were also identified through GC-MS.

Keywords : *Azadirachta indica*, Meliaceae, neem root bark, non-terpenoids.

Introduction

Azadirachta indica A. Juss (Meliaceae), the neem tree, widely distributed in dry areas of the tropics and subtropics¹, has been the subject of studies since about the beginning of last century due to its varied biological activities^{2,3}. As a result, a large number of terpenoidal⁴⁻⁷ as well as non-terpenoidal constituents^{8,9} have been reported by various groups of workers. In continuation of our work, herein we report on the isolation and characterization of two steroids and ferula aldehyde along with the identification of fatty acid components of root bark. The hitherto unreported ¹H NMR data of ferula-aldehyde is also described in the present paper. Only six fatty acids were present in the petrol-soluble fraction of the root bark.

Results and discussion

The two sterols, margocidin (1) and 3 β -hydroxy stigmast-5-ene (2) were initially isolated as one component as they showed a single spot on tlc and the mass spectrum showed only one very clear molecular ion peak at *m/z* 428 with successive losses of methyl and ethyl groups. The peak matching of the molecular ion led to deduce the molecular formula as C₂₉H₄₈O₂ and the positive Liebermann-Buchardt test indicated their sterolic nature. The NMR spectra (¹H and ¹³C), however, indicated that these are a mixture of two sterols showing over-

lapped spots on tlc. Several initial attempts to resolve these on tlc failed, but GC of the acetylated product clearly showed two peaks of nearly same intensity. These acetyl derivatives could be ultimately separated on precoated thin layer cards of alumina developed in CHCl₃.

Margocidin formed a diacetyl derivative (1a) and therefore its two oxygen functions were attributed to two hydroxyl groups. Further, as the molecular formula showed six unsaturations and a positive sterolic test, presence of two C-C double bonds was considered apart from four rings of the steroidal skeleton. The characteristic one-proton triplet at δ 5.33 (*J* 3.69 Hz) and a one-proton multiplet at δ 3.65 (*W*/2 = 18.5 Hz) were attributed to H-6 and H-3 α (axial) respectively. Two one-proton double doublet at δ 4.05 (*J*_{gem} 15.6, *J*_{29a,28} 6.6 Hz, H-29a) and δ 4.16 (*J*_{gem} 15.6, *J*_{29b,28} 5.4 Hz, H-29b) and a one-proton multiplet at δ 5.08 (H-28) led to locate the second double bond at C-24 (C-28) and hydroxyl group at C-29 [11]. Besides, the ¹H NMR spectrum showed two singlets at δ 0.73 and δ 0.83 for the angular methyl protons, a six-proton doublet at δ 0.90 (*J* 6.30 Hz) for H-26 and H-27 and a three-proton doublet at δ 0.89 (*J* 7.30 Hz) for H-21. The functionalities noted above were favoured by ¹³C NMR data (Broad Band and DEPT) which showed a tertiary (δ 73.3) and a secondary (δ 68.2) carbinyl carbon, two quaternary (δ 138.9, 138.1) and two secondary

[†]In honour of Professor Sunil Kumar Talapatra on the occasion of his 80th birthday.

(δ 130.8, 128.8) olefinic carbons. These features led to define the structure of margocidin as **1** which was finally confirmed by significant fragments at m/z 273 [M^+ -side chain], 255 [273-18] $^+$, 241 and 227 resulting from the cleavages of ring D, followed by the successive losses of a water molecule. Margocidin has not been reported earlier as a natural product although its synthesis is reported in literature¹⁰ alongwith its cytotoxicity towards spleen lymphocytes and significant immune suppressive properties¹¹. Ferula aldehyde was characterized by comparing its spectral data with those reported in literature²², while the second sterol was identified as 3 β -hydroxy stigmaster-5-en-7-one (**2**) through comparison of its physical data with those reported earlier¹³.

Table 1. ^{13}C NMR Spectral data (ppm) of (**1**) and (**2**) (CDCl_3 ; 100 MHz)

Assignment	δ_{C} (1)	δ_{C} (2)
C-1	37.1	38.0
C-2	31.9	31.8
C-3	73.3	73.3
C-4	42.5	42.5
C-5	138.1	168.3
C-6	124.8	126.4
C-7	32.4	200.5
C-8	32.4	32.4
C-9	50.2	51.2
C-10	37.1	37.1
C-11	21.0	21.0
C-12	39.7	39.7
C-13	42.5	42.5
C-14	55.9	56.1
C-15	24.2	24.2
C-16	28.9	28.9
C-17	56.1	55.9
C-18	12.2	12.0
C-19	19.5	19.8
C-20	36.1	36.1
C-21	19.1	19.1
C-22	34.0	34.0
C-23	29.3	29.3
C-24	138.9	50.2
C-25	31.9	26.2
C-26	21.0	19.8
C-27	19.1	18.7
C-28	130.8	23.1
C-29	68.2	12.0

Table 2. Fatty acid components of neem root bark

Fatty acids	Root bark
Nonanoic acid	+
Hexadecanoic acid	+
Octadecatrienoic acid	+
Octadecanoic acid	+
Henicosenoic acid	+
Tetracosanoic acid	+

Experimental

M.p.s uncorr. The NMR spectra were obtained in CDCl_3 on a Bruker 400 MHz NMR spectrometer operating at 400 MHz for ^1H and 100 MHz for ^{13}C NMR

(Broad Bond, DEPT). Chemical shifts are reported in ppm (δ) and coupling constants (J) are in Hz. The assignments of ^{13}C NMR chemical shifts are based on chemical shift rules¹⁴ and comparison with similar compounds^{15,16}. The EIMS were recorded on a Finnigan-MAT 311 mass spectrometer at 250 °C and 70 eV. GCMS were recorded on MAT 112 mass spectrometer connected to Varian 3700 gas chromatograph fitted with a 0.3 mm capillary glass column of sp 2100. Temperature programming was from 70–250 °C at 8°/min. E energy emission current and ion source temperature of the mass spectrometer were 80 eV, 0.7 mA and 270 °C respectively. UV spectra (MeOH) were run on Hitachi-U-3200 spectrophotometer and IR spectra (CHCl_3) were obtained using a JASCO-A-302 spectrophotometer. Merck Kieselgel 60 PF 254 and alumina coated on glass plates were used for analytical and prep. TLC.

Plant material :

The root bark (5 kg) of neem (*Azadirachta indica* A. Juss) was collected from the Karachi region in the month of February and identified by Mr. Sherwali (Herbarium Incharge), Department of Botany, University of Karachi. A voucher specimen (NM-1) has been deposited in the Herbarium, Department of Botany, University of Karachi.

Extraction and isolation :

Neem root bark (5 kg) collected from Karachi region was repeatedly extracted with *n*-hexane and the oily residue left on removal of the solvent from the combined *n*-hexane extract was kept aside for the determination of fatty acid components. The defatted bark was repeatedly percolated with CH_2Cl_2 at room temperature and combined extract was freed of the solvent under reduced pressure. The residue obtained was treated with *n*-hexane to separate *n*-hexane-soluble and -insoluble fractions. The latter fraction was treated with EtOAc to give EtOAc-soluble and -insoluble fractions. The EtOAc-soluble fraction was concentrated and poured in an excess of *n*-hexane to afford *n*-hexane-EtOAc-soluble and -insoluble fractions, respectively. The residue from the *n*-hexane-EtOAc-soluble fraction was subjected to flash column chromatography (*n*-hexane, *n*-hexane-EtOAc, in the order of increasing polarity). The *n*-hexane-EtOAc (9 : 1) eluate of flash column afforded ferula aldehyde (3) as a pure compound whereas *n*-hexane-EtOAc (8 : 2) eluate yielded a

mixture of magrocin (1) and 3 β -hydroxy stigmast-5-en-7-one (2) showing a single spot on tlc. This mixture was acetylated with Ac_2O and pyridine under usual conditions and the acetylated product was separated on precoated thin layer cards of alumina and developed in CHCl_3 . On hydrolysis with methanolic KOH (2%) at room temperature overnight and usual work-up, pure 1 and 2 were ultimately obtained.

Margocidin (1) (8.8 mg). On recrystallization from MeOH it formed irregular plates m.p. 108–109°; HR-EIMS m/z (rel. int.) : 428.3653 [M^+] (calcd. for $\text{C}_{29}\text{H}_{48}\text{O}_2$, 428.3654) (100), 413.3419 (M-15) (18); EIMS m/z (rel. int.) : 428 (100), 413 (22), 313 (16), 273 (8), 255 (10), 241 (20) and 227 (96).

Ferula aldehyde (3) (3.4 mg). It crystallized from benzene as plates m.p. 84–85°; HR-EIMS m/z (rel. int.) : 178.0643 (M^+ , calcd. for $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_3$, 178.0629) (26), 161.0602 (M-17) (38) and 147.0446 (M-31) (30); ^1H NMR δ : 3.94 (3H, s, OCH_3), 6.58 (1H, dd, J 15.80, 8.12 Hz, H-2'), 6.94 (1H, d, J 8.22 Hz, H-5), 7.05 (1H, d, J 2.00 Hz, H-2), 7.11 (1H, dd, J 8.22, 2.00 Hz, H-6), 7.37 (1H, d, J 15.80 Hz, H-3') and 9.65 (1H, d, J 8.12 Hz, H-1').

Fatty acids :

The *n*-hexane-soluble fraction, referred to above, was hydrolysed with 5% methanolic KOH for 2 h on boiling water bath. It was diluted with water and shaken with EtOAc to separate out the unsaponifiable matter. The aqueous alkaline phase was acidified with 10% HCl and shaken with EtOAc. The residue obtained from EtOAc phase after usual work-up was taken in Et_2O and methylated with freshly prepared CH_2N_2 by keeping the reactants at room temperature over night. The methyl esters were analysed by GCMS and the acids identified through their methyl esters are listed in Table 2.

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